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In Situ Transesterification of Rubber Seeds (*Hevea brasiliensis*)

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Biodiesel is a methyl or ethyl fatty acid esters formed by transesterifying vegetable oils (both edible and non edible) or animal fats. In this research, biodiesel is produced by in-situ transesterification (direct transesterification) method from the seeds of rubber tree using KOH as a catalyst. The influence of methanol to seeds ratio, reaction time, temperature and catalyst concentration was investigated. Important properties of biodiesel such as free fatty acid (FFA), viscosity, pour point, density etc were also investigated. The result shows that the best ratio of seeds to methanol was 1:6 (10 g seeds with 60 g methanol), 120 minutes reaction time at 60°C reaction temperature and catalyst concentration of 2.5 g. The maximum yield obtain was 74.5%. This study supports the production of biodiesel from the rubber seeds using direct transesterification method from the seeds as an alternative to diesel fuel.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Viscosity, FAME, Free fatty acid, In situ, Rubber seeds.

INTRODUCTION

The rubber tree (*Hevea brasiliensis*) is a perennial plantation crop, originated from South America and cultivated as an industrial crop since its introduction to Southeast Asia in 1876. The rubber trees growth is most rapid at altitudes below 200 m and with monthly mean temperatures of about 27 or 28°C which is appropriate in ASIAN countries. In recent years, the use of biodiesels as alternative fuels has been extensively investigated with the objective of ensuring energy security and reducing the environmental impacts of diesel emissions. Rubber seed oil (RSO) has potential to become a prominent resource as it is non-edible. Natural rubber producers in the world are Thailand (35%), Indonesia (23%), Malaysia (12%), India (9%), and China (7%). Normal seed production yields vary from 70 to 500 kg/ha/year (Ikwaagwu and Njoku, 2000) while in Malaysia the trees cover more than 1.2 million ha all over the country and each hectare can give an approximate amount of 150 kg of rubber seeds (Yusuf and Khan, 2010). Rubber tree has many advantages, apart from its used in latex production in plastic industries it could as well as be used in biodiesel production. It is also employed as an alternative low-cost adsorbent for the removal of malachite green from aqueous solutions (Le Phan Lihn et al., 2012).

Table 1: Composition of rubber seeds (AbdulShokib and Rachimoellah, 2010)

Composition	Content (%)
Oil	45.63
Ash	2.71
Water	3.71
Protein	22.17
Carbohydrate	24.21
Others	1.57

Worry over current energy scarcity and environmental restrictions have raised interest in the development and use of non-petroleum-based renewable fuels. One attractive alternative is biodiesel, which is an oxygenated, diesel-like fuel consisting of fatty acid alkyl esters (most commonly fatty acid methyl esters, or FAMES) that are derived from oils and fats. The most commonly used method for biodiesel production is transesterification of vegetable oils or fats with

methanol or ethanol in the presence of a catalyst (Ali et al., 2012; Warale, 2007 in Borin, 2004). But biodiesel production process can save cost if use *in situ* transesterification. In this process, costs for solvent extraction and purification of oil can be reduced, so biodiesel production is becoming simpler and easier (Harrington and Catherine, 1985).

In situ transesterification is a method used to produce biodiesel by contacting raw materials (seed) directly with an alcohol assisted with an acid/alkaline catalyst. Theoretically, transesterification reaction requires three moles of alcohol for each mole of oil. In the process of *in situ* transesterification with either an acid or alkaline catalyst, molar ratio of alcohol/seeds is much higher than the value calculated based on the stoichiometry of the transesterification reaction. Excess methanol will play the role of the extraction solvent as well as a reactant (Hincapie et al. 2011).

The method (*in situ*) transesterification was introduced by Harrington and Catherine (1985). They use sunflower seeds as a raw material. Siler-Marinkovic and Tomasevic (1998) did experiments with the same process. Ozgul (1993) and Sevil Ozgul-Yucel (2002) used *in situ* esterification with rice bran as raw materials and ethanol and methanol as solvent; and also Ginting et al. (2011) did *in situ* transesterification from castor seed (*Jatropha curcas*). Widayata and Suherman (2012) produced biodiesel from the rubber seed via Esterification Process. Mondala et al. (2008) synthesized biodiesel by *in situ* transesterification of municipal primary and secondary sludge and found that, the yield of FAMES from primary sludge was significantly affected by the interactive effects of temperature, catalyst concentration, and methanol to sludge mass ratio, while the yield of FAMES from secondary sludge was significantly affected by the independent effects of the three factors investigated.

Transesterification (alcoholysis) is the chemical reaction between triglycerides and alcohol in the presence of catalyst to produce mono-esters. The long and branched chain triglyceride molecules are transformed to monoesters and glycerin (Ma, 1999). Transesterification process consists of a sequence of three consecutive reversible reactions. That is, conversion of triglycerides to diglycerides, followed by the conversion of diglycerides to monoglycerides. The glycerides are converted into glycerol and yielding one ester molecule in each step. The properties of these esters are comparable to that of diesel.

The objective of this research is to produce biodiesel from rubber seeds by *in situ* transesterification method and study the influence of mass ratio of rubber seed to methanol, temperature of the reaction, reaction time, size of the seeds, and alkaline catalyst concentration on the FAME yield.

Experimental procedure

Sample preparation

Rubber trees yield 3-seeded ellipsoidal capsules, each capsule with one seed. Rubber seeds are ellipsoidal, variable in size, 2.5–3cm long, mottled brown, lustrous, weighing 2–4 g each. Capsules are spread over the ground. The seeds were collected from a plantation nearby Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Perak Malaysia and dried under the sun for about three hours to remove the remaining moisture, and then the kernels were separated by breaking the capsules. The kernels were dried in the oven for about 24 hours to remove the remaining moisture. The seeds were immediately grounded using food processing machine (blender) in order to weaken and rupture of the cell. Subsequently, the grounded rubber seed was taken into the oven and stay overnight at 104 °C in order to deactivate the remaining enzyme as well as to remove the moisture and then sieved using 300, 350 and 400 µm opening screens. Finally three different size fractions were obtained; 150 µm (0-300 µm), 325 µm (300-350 µm), and 375 µm (350-400 µm).

Transesterification process

10g rubber seeds sample was taken into the 3 neck round bottom flask. Methanol and KOH catalyst was added and heated at 60°C at atmospheric pressure for 120 minutes. The mixture was stirred throughout the reaction at 400rpm. The product was filtered and poured into the separating funnel for separating the excess of alcohol and glycerol. Also, warm water was added to the mixture in order to enhance glycerol separation. The product was investigated for the effect of mass ratio of the seeds to methanol, catalyst concentration, reaction time, sizes of the seeds, and the effect of temperature on the yield. The concentration analysis of FAME was performed by using Agilent 7890A Gas Chromatography (GC) equipped with Flame Ionization Detector (FID). Automatic injection sampler was used by an Agilent auto injector. The column configuration used was, 30m x 0.25mm ID, 0.25 µm DB-wax (J & W 122-7032).

Methyl heptadecanoate (10.0 mg; internal standard) was dissolved in 1 ml hexane to prepare the standard solution. Approximately 100 mg crude methyl ester was dissolved in 1 ml standard solution for GC analysis. Approximately 1 µl sample was injected into the GC at an oven temperature of 210 °C with Helium as the carrier gas.

The FAME yield was calculated from the following expressions:

$$\text{Yield} = \frac{\text{Actual weight (g)}}{\text{Theoretical weight (g)}} \times 100\%$$

PROPERTIES OF THE FAME PRODUCED

The fuel properties of rubber seed methyl ester in relationship with that of other esters is shown in Table 2 (Ramadhas et al., 2005a). The density and specific gravity at 20°C was measured by using the Anton Paar DMA 4500 M Density Meter in accordance with the testing method of ASTM D 4052. Viscosity is one of the most important properties of the biodiesel and it was measured by using Brookfield CAP 200+ following ASTM D 445 method at constant temperature of 40°C. Pour point was measured by using the CPP 5G's analyzer by following the ASTM D 2500. The acid value/FFA was determined by titration method according to AOCS method (Firestone, 1998). The majority of the properties of the obtained FAME through *in situ* transesterification method are relatively equivalent to those of other esters. The GC-FID analysis shows that, the biodiesel contains large amount of C18. The present result shows that, the *in situ* transesterification process enhanced the fuel properties of the oil with respect to specific gravity, viscosity, density, and acid value. The viscosity of biodiesel is in the range of biodiesel standard. The properties of the obtained biodiesel are in comparable with ASTM standards. The observed properties of methyl esters from rubber seed by *in situ* transesterification method are found to be in reasonable conformity with ASTM 6751.

Table 2: Properties of methyl esters of rubber seed oil in comparison with other esters (Ramadhas et al., 2005a)

S/N	Property	Testing procedure	Biodiesel standard ASTM 6751-02	Rubber seed oil FAME (by <i>in situ</i>)	Rape seed oil FAME	Soybean oil FAME
1	Specific gravity at 20°C	ASTM D4052	0.87–0.90	0.874	0.882	0.885
2	Viscosity (cP) at 40°C	ASTM D445	1.9–6.0	7.2	4.5	4.08
3	Pour point (°C)	ASTM D97	-15 to 10	4.8	-12	-3
4	Acid value (mg KOH/g)	ASTM D974	0.8	0.65	NA	NA
5	Density at 20°C (g/cm ³)	ASTM D4052	-	0.897	NA	NA
6	FFA	ASTM D974	<1.0	0.3	NA	NA

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Effect of seed to alcohol mass ratio

The mass ratio of alcohol to seeds is one of the important factors that affect the conversion efficiency as well as production cost of biodiesel. Mass ratio is the ratio of number of mass of alcohol to number of mass of rubber seeds. The conversion efficiency is defined as the yield of the process represented in terms of percentage (Ramadhas et al., 2005b). In this research, various mass ratios of the seeds to methanol starting with 1:2 and followed by (1:3, 1:4, 1:5, 1:6, 1:7 and 1:8) were tested. It was found that the maximum yield was achieved at the mass ratio of 1:6 (74.5%) at 60 °C reaction temperature, 120 minutes reaction time, <300 µm seed sizes and 3 g KOH catalyst as shown in figure below, further increase in mass ratio there was no any improvement in the yield.

Figure 1: Effects of molar ratio of seeds to alcohol on the FAME yield (%)

Effect of reaction temperature

Different temperatures ranging from 40 to 60°C (40, 45.50 55, 60, 65 and 70°C) were investigated. At a lower temperature (40°C) the yield was low (about 42%). But with increase in temperature the conversion rate was very fast. The optimum temperature for this reaction was found to be in the range of 55-60°C, which was about 74.6% yield with 1:6 mass ratio, 120 minutes reaction time, <300 μm seed sizes and 3 g KOH catalyst as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Effects of reaction temperature on the FAME yield (%)

The reaction temperature greater than 60°C should be avoided in the case of rubber seed, because they tend to accelerate saponification of the glycerides by the alkaline catalyst before completion of the alcoholysis (Ramadas et al., 2005a).

The reason for the increase in yield is that increase in temperature is believed to facilitate the breaking of seeds cell walls, thereby creating a void which serves as migratory space for the contents of the oil-bearing cells. Temperature also lowers the viscosity of the oil, thus facilitating the release of the oil out of the cells into the kernel. However, at higher temperature, there is substantial loss of moisture leading to a hardening of samples and oil degradation. This may account for the decrease in the ester content and the yield at higher temperature (Thaiyasuit, 2009).

Effect of reaction duration

A Various reaction duration starting from 40, 60, 80 100,120,140 and 160 minutes were investigated. The maximum ester yield obtained in this experiment was 75% as shown in figure 3 at 120 minutes reaction time, at 60°C reaction temperature, 1:6 mass ratio, <300 μm seed sizes and 3 g KOH catalyst. Further increase in this reaction time, there was no any observed improvement.

Figure 3: Effects of reaction time on the FAME yield (%)

Effect of catalyst concentration

The alkaline catalyst, potassium hydroxide concentration in the range of 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5 and 4.0g was used in this experimental analysis. The effect of catalyst amount on the yield is shown in Figure 4. The maximum yield is achieved at 2.5% and 3.0% of KOH which is 75% at 60 °C, with 1:6 mass ratio, 120 minutes reaction time, and <300 μm seed sizes. Addition of excess amount of catalyst, gave rise to the formation of an emulsion, which increased the viscosity and led to the formation of gels. Esterification does not take place for insufficient amount of catalyst (Sevil Ozgul-Yucel, 2002). As mentioned by Ramadhas et al. (2005b), from physical appearance the higher catalyst concentration, the darker also biodiesel produced. Therefore the addition of a suitable catalyst concentration is important to the physical appearance of biodiesel.

Figure 4: Effects of catalyst concentration on the FAME yield (%)

Effect of sizes of the seeds on the yield of ester content

Various sizes of the seeds ranging from 300-400 μm mesh sizes was used, it has been observed that, the maximum yield of 74% was achieved at the smaller mesh sizes of 300 μm with 1:6 mass ratio at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ reaction temperature, 120 minutes reaction time, and 3 g KOH catalyst as shown in figure 5.

Figure 5: Effect of mesh size (μm) on the biodiesel yield (%)

This phenomenon could be attributed to the fact that smaller particles have larger amount of surface area as well as an increased number of broken cells resulting in a high oil concentration at the particle surface (Thaiyasuit, 2009).

CONCLUSION

In-situ transesterification of rubber seeds using the mixture of methanol and KOH as alkaline catalyst had been done. The reaction was carried out for 10 grams of dry seeds in various mass ratio of methanol to seeds from 1:2 to 1:6, different temperatures ranging from 40 to 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, varying of the reaction time, sizes of the seeds and various catalyst concentrations from 1.0 to 3.0 wt%. Therefore, this research revealed that, biodiesel can be produced by *in situ* transesterification method from the seeds of rubber tree, and it was found that the maximum yield of biodiesel obtained was 75% at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with mass ratio of 1:6, 2.5% (w/v) of KOH as catalyst, stirring speed of 400 rpm for 120 minutes. The results were also in agreement with the findings of a previous study by Widayata and Suherman (2012) on Production Process of Biodiesel from Rubber Seeds (*Hevea Brasiliensis*) by *In Situ* Transesterification Method with Alkaline Catalyzed.

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